

OSCILLATORY FLOW OF A FLUID
BETWEEN TWO INFINITE PLATES WITH AN EFFECT OF HEAT TRANSFER

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we examine the effect of heat transfer on oscillatory flow of a Newtonian fluid between two infinite parallel plates under the influence of inclined magnetic field. It is assumed that the fluid has small electrical conductivity and the electromagnetic force produced is very small. The governing coupled momentum and energy equations are solved and the expressions for velocity and temperature fields are obtained analytically. The effects of various emerging parameters on the velocity field, temperature field, skin friction and Nusselt number are discussed in detail with the aid of graphs and tables.

Keywords: Oscillatory flow, inclined magnetic field, heat transfer, temperature field, velocity field.

1. INTRODUCTION

The flow of an electrically conducting fluid has significant applications in many branches of engineering science such as magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) generators, plasma studies, nuclear reactor, geothermal energy extraction, electromagnetic propulsion, the boundary layer control in the field of aerodynamics and so on. Heat transfer effect on laminar flow between parallel plates under the action of transverse magnetic field was studied by Nigam and Singh [9]. Soundalgekar and Bhat [12] have investigated the MHD oscillatory flow of a Newtonian fluid in a channel with heat transfer. MHD flow of viscous fluid between two parallel plates with heat transfer was discussed by Attia, and Koth [2]. Raptis *et al.* [10] have analyzed the hydromagnetic free convection flow through a porous medium between two parallel plates. Aldoss *et al.* [1] have studied mixed convection flow from a vertical plate embedded in a porous medium in the presence of a magnetic field. Makinde and Mhone [6] have considered heat transfer to MHD oscillatory flow in a channel filled with porous medium. Mostafa[8] have studied thermal radiation effect on unsteady MHD free convection flow past a vertical plate with temperature dependent viscosity. Unsteady heat transfer to MHD oscillatory flow through a porous medium under slip condition was investigated by Hamza *et al.*[4]. Manyonge *et al.*[7] have studied the steady MHD Poiseuille flow between two infinite parallel porous plates in an inclined magnetic field. The effect of an inclined magnetic field on unsteady free convection flow of a dusty viscous fluid between two infinite flat plates filled by a porous medium was investigated by Sandeep and Sugunamma [11]. Recently, Joseph *et al.* [5] have analyzed the unsteady MHD couette flow between two infinite parallel porous plates in an inclined magnetic field with Heat Transfer.

In view of these, we modeled the effect of heat transfer on oscillatory flow of a fluid between two infinite parallel plates under the effect of inclined magnetic field. The expressions for the velocity and temperature fields are obtained analytically. The effects various emerging parameters on the velocity field, temperature field, skin friction and Nusselt number are discussed in detail with the aid of graphs and tables.

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2. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

We consider the oscillatory flow of a Newtonian fluid in a channel of width h under the influence of inclined magnetic field and radiative heat transfer as depicted in Fig.1. It is assumed that the fluid has small electrical conductivity and the electromagnetic force produced is very small. We choose the Cartesian coordinate system (x, y) , where x - is taken along center of the channel and the y - axis is taken normal to the flow direction.

Fig. 1 Physical model of the problem

The basic equations of momentum (Joseph, 2014) and energy governing such a flow, subject to the Boussinesq approximation, are:

$$\rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \sigma B_0^2 \sin^2(\alpha) u + \rho g \beta (T - T_0) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{k}{c_p} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{c_p} \frac{\partial q}{\partial y} \quad (2.2)$$

The boundary conditions are given by

$$u = 0, T = T_0 \quad \text{at} \quad y = 0 \quad (2.3)$$

$$u = 0, T = T_1 \quad \text{at} \quad y = h \quad (2.4)$$

where $\alpha (0 \leq \alpha \leq \pi)$ is the angle between velocity and magnetic field strength, u is the axial velocity, T is the fluid temperature, p is the pressure, ρ is the fluid density, B_0 is the magnetic field strength, σ is the conductivity of the fluid, g is the acceleration due to gravity, β is the coefficient of volume expansion due to temperature, c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure, k is the thermal conductivity and q is the radiative heat flux. Following Cogley *et al.* (1968), it is assumed that the fluid is optically thin with a relatively low density and the radiative heat flux is given by

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial y} = 4\alpha_1^2 (T_0 - T) \quad (2.5)$$

where α_1 is the mean radiation absorption coefficient.

Introducing the following non-dimensional variables

$$\bar{x} = \frac{x}{h}, \quad \bar{y} = \frac{y}{h}, \quad \bar{u} = \frac{u}{U}, \quad \theta = \frac{T - T_0}{T_1 - T_0}, \quad \bar{t} = \frac{tU}{h}, \quad \bar{p} = \frac{pa}{\mu U}, \quad M^2 = \frac{\sigma h^2 B_0^2}{\mu}, \quad Gr = \frac{\rho g \beta (T_1 - T_0)}{U \mu},$$

$$Re = \frac{\rho h U}{\mu}, \quad Pe = \frac{\rho h U c_p}{k}, \quad N^2 = \frac{4\alpha_1^2 h^2}{k}$$

where U is the mean flow velocity, into the equations (2.1) and (2.2), we get (after dropping bars)

$$Re \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - M_1^2 u + Gr \theta \quad (2.6)$$

$$Pe \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} + N^2 \theta \tag{2.7}$$

where Re is the Reynolds number, $M_1 = M \sin \alpha$, M is the Hartmann number, Gr is the Grashof number, Pe is the Peclet number and N is the radiation parameter.

The corresponding non-dimensional boundary conditions are

$$u = 0, \theta = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad y = 0 \tag{2.8}$$

$$u = 0, \theta = 1 \quad \text{at} \quad y = 1 \tag{2.9}$$

3. SOLUTION

In order to solve equations (2.6) – (2.9) for purely oscillatory flow, let

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \lambda e^{i\omega t} \tag{3.1}$$

$$u(y, t) = u_0(y) e^{i\omega t} \tag{3.2}$$

$$\theta(y, t) = \theta_0(y) e^{i\omega t} \tag{3.3}$$

where λ is a real constant and ω is the frequency of the oscillation.

Substituting the equations (3.1) - (3.3) in to the equations (2.6) – (2.9), we get

$$\frac{d^2 u_0}{dy^2} - m_2^2 u_0 = -\lambda - Gr \theta_0 \tag{3.4}$$

$$\frac{d^2 \theta_0}{dy^2} + m_1^2 \theta_0 = 0 \tag{3.5}$$

with the boundary conditions

$$u_0 = 0, \theta_0 = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad y = 0 \tag{3.6}$$

$$u_0 = 0, \theta_0 = 1 \quad \text{at} \quad y = 1 \tag{3.7}$$

In which $m_1 = \sqrt{N^2 - i\omega Pe}$ and $m_2 = \sqrt{M_1^2 + i\omega Re}$.

Solving equations (3.4) and (3.5) using the boundary conditions (3.6) and (3.7), we obtain

$$u_0(y) = \left(\frac{Gr}{(m_1^2 + m_2^2)} \left[\frac{\sin m_1 y}{\sin m_1} - \frac{\sinh m_2 y}{\sinh m_2} \right] + \frac{\lambda (\cos m_2 - 1) \sinh m_2 y}{m_2^2 \sinh m_2} \right) + \frac{\lambda}{m_2^2} (1 - \cosh m_2 y) \tag{3.8}$$

$$\text{and } \theta_0(y) = \frac{\sin m_1 y}{\sin m_1} \tag{3.9}$$

Therefore, the fluid velocity and temperature are given as

$$u(y, t) = \left(\frac{Gr}{(m_1^2 + m_2^2)} \left[\frac{\sin m_1 y}{\sin m_1} - \frac{\sinh m_2 y}{\sinh m_2} \right] + \frac{\lambda (\cos m_2 - 1) \sinh m_2 y}{m_2^2 \sinh m_2} \right) + \frac{\lambda}{m_2^2} (1 - \cosh m_2 y) \Bigg) e^{i\omega t} \tag{3.10}$$

$$\text{and } \theta(y,t) = \frac{\sin m_1 y}{\sin m_1} e^{i\omega t} \quad (3.11)$$

The skin friction at the upper plate $y = 1$ of the channel is given by

$$\tau = -\left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right|_{y=1} = - \left(\frac{Gr}{(m_1^2 + m_2^2)} [m_1 \cot m_1 - m_2 \coth m_2] + \frac{\lambda (\cos m_2 - 1)}{m_2} \coth m_2 - \frac{\lambda}{m_2} \sinh m_2 \right) e^{i\omega t} \quad (3.12)$$

The rate of heat transfer coefficient in terms of Nusselt number Nu at the plate $y = 1$ of the channel is given by

$$Nu = -\left. \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right|_{y=1} = -(m_1 \cot m_1) e^{i\omega t} \quad (3.13)$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Velocity Profiles

In order to see the effects of various physical parameters like N , Gr , Re , ω , M , λ , Pe and α on the velocity profile u we have plotted the Figs. 2-9.

Fig (2) illustrates the variation of velocity with respect to 'y' for various values of $\alpha = 0, \frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2}$ at $N=1, Gr=1, Re=1, \omega=1, M=1, \lambda = 1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$. It is found that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as we go from cold plate to hot plate. Also it is observed that the velocity u decreases with increasing inclination angle α .

Fig (3) demonstrates the effect of Hartmann number (M) on the velocity u with respect to 'y'. Figure corresponds for the values $N=1, Gr=1, Re=1, \omega = 1, \alpha = \frac{\pi}{4}, \lambda = 1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$. It is noted that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y increases. Also it is observed that the velocity u decreases with an increase in Hartmann number M .

Fig (4) shows the effect of Radiation parameter N on the velocity u with respect to 'y'. Here $\alpha = \frac{\pi}{4}, Gr=1, Re=1, \omega = 1, M=1, \lambda = 1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$ are considered to draw the figure. It is seen that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as we go from cold plate to hot plate. Also it is found that the velocity u increases with increasing Radiation parameter N .

Fig (5) illustrates the variation of velocity u with respect to 'y' for various values of $N=1, \alpha = \frac{\pi}{4}, Re=1, \omega = 1, M=1, \lambda = 1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$. This figure corresponds to Grashoff number $Gr=10, 5, 1$. Here it is found that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y increases. Also it is seen that the velocity u increases with an increase in Grashoff number Gr .

Fig (6) communicates the effect of Reynolds number Re on the velocity u with respect to 'y'. This figure corresponds to $N=1, Gr=1, \alpha = \frac{\pi}{4}, \omega = 1, M=1, \lambda = 1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$. It is observed that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y advances. Also it is seen that the velocity u decreases with increasing Reynolds number Re .

Fig (7) depicts the variation of velocity u with respect to 'y' at $N=1, Gr=1, Re=1, \omega = 1, M=1, \lambda = 1, \alpha = \frac{\pi}{4}$, and $t=0$. This figure corresponds to Peclet number $Pe=7, 1, 0.71$. It is noted that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y increases. Also it is observed that the velocity u increases with increasing Peclet number Pe .

Fig (8) shows the variation of velocity u with respect to 'y' for various values of frequency of oscillations $\omega = 1, 2, 3$. This figure corresponds to $N=1, Gr=1, Re=1, \alpha = \frac{\pi}{4}, M=1, \lambda = 1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$. From the figure it is observed that It is observed that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y advances. It is also noted that the velocity u decreases with an increase in frequency of oscillations ω .

Fig (9) shows the effect of pressure gradient parameter λ on the velocity u with respect to 'y'. This figure corresponds to $N=1, Gr=1, Re=1, \omega = 1, M=1, \alpha = \frac{\pi}{4}, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$. It is seen that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as 'y' advances. It is also observed that the velocity u increases with increasing Pressure constant λ .

Table-1 shows the effects of $N, Gr, Re, \omega, M, \lambda, Pe$ and α on the skin friction τ . From Table-1, it is observed that the skin friction τ decreases with increasing α, M, Re and ω , whereas it increases with increasing N, Gr, Pe and λ .

4.2 Temperature profiles

In order to see the effects of various physical parameters like N, ω and Pe on the temperature profiles θ we have plotted the Figs. 10-12.

Fig (10) communicates the variation of temperature θ for various values of Radiation parameter N . From the figure it is found that the temperature θ increases with increasing radiation parameter N . It is observed that θ firstly increases and then decreases for $N=2$ and $N=3$, and the graph takes almost linear form for $N=1$. Also it is seen that the variation in temperature from $N=3$ to $N=2$ is more widely visible than the variation in temperature from $N=2$ to $N=1$.

Fig (11) depicts the variation of temperature θ for various values of Peclet number $Pe=0.71, 1, 7$. This corresponds to $\omega = 1, N=1$ and $t=0$. From the figure it is observed that the temperature θ decreases with an increase in Peclet number Pe .

Fig (12) illustrates the effect of frequency of oscillations ω on the temperature θ for $N=1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$. It is noted that the temperature θ decreases with increasing frequency of oscillations ω .

Table-2 shows the effects of N, ω and Pe on the Nusselt number Nu at the upper plate. From Table-2, it is found that the Nusselt number Nu increase with increasing N , while it decreases with increasing Pe and ω .

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this chapter, we studied the effect of heat transfer on an oscillatory flow of a fluid between two infinite parallel plates under the influence of inclined magnetic field. The expressions for the velocity and temperature fields are obtained analytically. It is found that, the velocity u and skin friction τ increases with increasing N, Gr, Pe and λ , whereas they decreases with increasing α, M, Re and ω . The temperature θ and the Nusselt number Nu increases with increasing N , while they decreases with increasing Pe and ω .

Fig. 2 The effect of angle of inclination α on the velocity u for $N=1, Gr=1, Re=1, \omega=1, M=1, \lambda=1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$.

Fig. 3 The effect of Hartmann number M on the velocity u for $N=1, Gr=1, Re=1, \omega=1, \alpha=\pi/4, \lambda=1, Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$.

Fig. 4 The effect of radiation parameter N on the velocity u for $\alpha = \pi/4$, $Gr = 1$, $Re = 1$, $\omega = 1$, $M = 1$, $\lambda = 1$, $Pe = 0.71$ and $t = 0$.

Fig. 5 The effect of Grashof number Gr on the velocity u for $N = 1$, $\alpha = \pi/4$, $Re = 1$, $\omega = 1$, $M = 1$, $\lambda = 1$, $Pe = 0.71$ and $t = 0$.

Fig. 6 The effect of Reynolds number Re on the velocity u for $N = 1$, $Gr = 1$, $\alpha = \pi/4$, $\omega = 1$, $M = 1$, $\lambda = 1$, $Pe = 0.71$ and $t = 0$.

Fig. 7 The effect of Peclet number Pe on the velocity u for $N = 1$, $Gr = 1$, $Re = 1$, $\omega = 1$, $M = 1$, $\lambda = 1$, $\alpha = \pi/4$ and $t = 0$.

Fig. 8 The effect of frequency of oscillations ω on the velocity u for $N = 1$, $Gr = 1$, $Re = 1$, $\alpha = \pi/4$, $M = 1$, $\lambda = 1$, $Pe = 0.71$ and $t = 0$.

Fig. 9 The effect of pressure gradient parameter λ on the velocity u for $N = 1$, $Gr = 1$, $Re = 1$, $\omega = 1$, $M = 1$, $\alpha = \pi/4$, $Pe = 0.71$ and $t = 0$.

Fig. 10 The effect of radiation parameter N on the temperature θ for $\omega=1$, $Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$.

Fig. 11 The effect of Peclet number Pe on the temperature θ for $\omega=1$, $N=1$ and $t=0$.

Fig. 12 The effect of frequency of oscillations ω on the temperature θ for $N=1$, $Pe=0.71$ and $t=0$.

Table-1 Skin friction τ for $t=0$.

α	M	N	Gr	Re	Pe	ω	λ	τ
$\pi/4$	1	1	1	1	0.71	1	1	0.5245
$\pi/2$	1	1	1	1	0.71	1	1	0.4197
$\pi/4$	2	1	1	1	0.71	1	1	0.2755
$\pi/4$	1	2	1	1	0.71	1	1	0.8447
$\pi/4$	1	1	5	1	0.71	1	1	0.7163
$\pi/4$	1	1	1	2	0.71	1	1	0.2508
$\pi/4$	1	1	1	1	7	1	1	0.8187
$\pi/4$	1	1	1	1	0.71	2	1	0.3204
$\pi/4$	1	1	1	1	0.71	1	2	1.0011

Table - 2 Nusselt number for $t=0$

N	Pe	ω	Nu
1	0.71	1	-0.6572
2	0.71	1	0.8657
1	7	1	-1.5824
1	0.71	2	-0.7013

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